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Research article**Optimizing Lot-Sizes and Scheduling in Terms of Mass Customization****Modrak Vladimir^{1,*}, Soltysova Zuzana¹ and Semanco Pavol²**

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Abstract The goal of mass customisation is to offer products tailored to the specific needs of the customers. Even though customers are aware that manufacturers need a certain time to produce and deliver customised products, the companies might guarantee that their products will arrive on time. Then, the objective of manufacturing managers is to minimise the total flow time of parts through the shop. One of the effective ways to reach this objective is to optimise schedules in order to satisfy the due date criterion, which plays a crucial role in the mass customisation environment. This paper, in the first part, outlines methodological tools to tackle the problem of shortening delivery times through scheduling and management of resources. In the second part of the paper, the proposed methodology framework through the theoretical example is applied.

Keywords: Batch size, Due date, Mass customisation, Scheduling software

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INTRODUCTION

Mass customisation (MC) includes several specific attributes, such as the ability to provide individually designed products. However, this marketing and manufacturing strategy brings some drawbacks for both customers and organisations. Changes in the mix of products usually lead to changes in loading among the different machines as they produce different volumes of jobs in a certain period of time (Chatzopoulos et al., 2011). Consequently, manufacturing lead times are substantially longer in comparison to the manufacturing of standardised products. According to Chandra and Kamrani (2004), customers are likely to be more willing to wait for customised products if delivery times are predictable and consistent. In this context, one of the challenges of MC is to focus on the development methods and tools to minimise delivery time and lead-time. In MC, the delivery time can be effectively minimised in several ways, e.g., by increasing the commonality between products, implementing group technology, and other approaches (Lau and Elaine, 2008). One of the effective ways to reach this objective is to optimise schedules in order to satisfy the due date criterion, which plays a crucial role in the mass customisation environment. For this purpose, methods of operations research are commonly employed. Even though manufacturing lead-time includes a more or less exact structure of time items, operations research focuses on substantial ones, such as flow times or/and make-span. Therefore, in our approach, only operational times will be assumed as critical ones. An actual task in scheduling approaches lies in reflecting new requirements on production optimisation. Numerous existing optimisation methods which were developed during previous decades followed requirements either for mass production or tailored production. However, mass customisation presents a paradox by combining customisation and mass production, and this new phenomenon opens a new field in operations research. This paper aims to propose a method that may contribute to the scheduling policies in terms of mass customised manufacturing. Its novelty consists of the generating optimised scheduling diagrams based on specification of an optimal pair of scheduling characteristics, which are represented by transport batch sizes and number of transport batches. The optimal scheduling parameters are obtained through the new approach by using specialised software.

This paper is divided into two main parts. The first part describes the methodological procedure for developing a production planning schedule in terms of mass customisation. The second part proposes methodology framework through the theoretical. Finally, the discussion and conclusion bring some relevant considerations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Related Works

Firstly, it could be useful to mention the existing literature reviews in the wider topic and scheduling problems of discrete processes, which offers a whole picture of the current literature. Chen et al. (2004) presented a comprehensive literature review on process planning and production scheduling in terms of mass customisation. The authors emphasise that: 'traditionally, process planning and production scheduling are considered as two isolated tasks and conducted by separate departments in manufacturing enterprises. Such isolation has become a major factor that limits the full utilization of manufacturing resources and adversely impacts overall performance.' Yao and Liu (2009) set up a dynamic and multi-objective optimisation mathematical model to solve optimisation and scheduling problems in mass customisation. Dou et al. (2016) developed an approach to customer-oriented product collaborative customisation in order to improve the design process. A novel optimisation for rescheduling workpieces was given by Gujjula and Günther (2009) and Valero-Herrero et al. (2014) proposed an innovative method on the resequencing problem by using several rules for placing and releasing workpieces. Gaia et al. (2002) studied the problem of assigning operations to an ordered sequence of non-identical workstations;

in their method, precedence relationships and cycle time restrictions were taken into consideration. The solution to the problem was based on a dynamic programming algorithm. Tabue and Minner (2018) defined the two-index vehicle flow formal description for the vehicle routing problem, whereas a multi-objective mixed-model assembly line sequencing problem related to routing problems was presented by Rahimi-Vahed et al. (2007). Related operational complexity issues of assembly processes were studied by literature, see for example, Modrak and Marton (2014) and Modrak and Soltysova (2017). Kim et al. (2000) developed a genetic algorithm in order to minimise the number of stations in a two-sided assembly line balancing problem., Castillo and Gazmuri (2015) viewed that the heuristics used in the batch scheduling problems are dispatching rules and built a batch sequence schedule, while Modrak and Pandian (2010) suggested an alternative heuristic algorithm for the flow shop scheduling problem to minimise completion time for the n-jobs m-machines problem, which can be effectively used in terms of a mass customisation environment. Later, the performance of the algorithm was successfully benchmarked with competitive constructive heuristics on actual theoretical flow shop problems (Semanco and Modrak, 2012). There are many scheduling software solutions for manufacturing optimisation, such as Fishbowl Manufacturing, NetSuite, JobBOSS, etc., but most of them are paid and focused on traditional production optimisation problems. Some of them need to be used only by educated workers or users with training. Due to this reason, we provide online available software, which is free and everyone can use it without need for training.

Proposed Methodology

The effective production of a high variety of products assumes using optimised scheduling methods with the purpose of reducing all waste time and minimising manufacturing lead-time. Scheduling in the mass-customised manufacturing is a typical multi-objective dynamic optimisation problem, which is constrained, especially, by stochastic demand, available production sources, and due dates. With the aim to contribute to solving such problems, we construct a novel dynamic scheduling model by considering the key features of the MC, namely, distinctive characteristics of customisation orders.

The first step of the proposed method is grouping individual orders (jobs) into the short time periods, e.g., daily quantities.

Subsequently, for each group of daily orders, we create $m \times n$ matrices with m machines and n jobs. Then, specific jobs of the given days might be divided into transport batch sizes (QT) and the number of transport batches (L). In the beginning, it is reasonable to set up minimal and maximal QT for each group of daily orders. Even though minimal makespan will be reached by using minimal $QT = 1$, it does not mean that such solution will satisfy defined criterion DD optimally. Therefore, trade-off between $QT = 1$ and $QT = QP$ in order to find sufficiently small lot- sizes is considered here as a proper way to solve the problem.

Due dates can be unified for each individual cumulative orders of the given days or can differ from each other. We will prefer to identify unified ones. In this case, DDs can be defined as the mean of minimal C_{max} values ($C_{maxmean}$) that can be obtained by setting transport batch sizes according to OPF. Then, the mean value is rounded to the nearest higher integer, and $DD \geq$ rounded $C_{maxmean}$.

After DD is determined, QT and L might be specified for each job of daily order. For this purpose, we need to find identical numbers of transport batches L for all jobs by using the formula:

$$L_i = \frac{QP_i}{QT_i}, \quad (1)$$

where QP_i – production batch size of the i -th job.

To demonstrate the procedure of finding optimal QT, the following example is used.

Let us say, that ordered quantities for jobs $Qp_1 = 107$, $Qp_2 = 43$ and $Qp_3 = 17$. Firstly, the ordered quantity of Qp_1 will be divided into two sub-jobs, e.g., $Qp_{1A} =$

100 and $Qp1B = 7$, $Qp2$ into $Qp2A = 40$ and $Qp2B = 3$, and $Qp3$ into $Qp3A = 10$ and $Qp3B = 7$.

Subsequently, it is possible to identify all alternative transport batch sizes by dividing all production batches of the given day by common divisors. Quantities of $Qp1A$, $Qp2A$ and $Qp3A$ are divisible by common divisors 1, 2, 5 and 10. Once the uniform numbers of transport batches L are known ($L = 1, 2, 5$ and 10), possible optimal transport batch sizes for $Qp1A$, $Qp2A$ and $Qp3A$ can be determined.

In the next step, C_{max} for each of four FSPs with the uniform number of transport batches is calculated by common heuristics, see, e.g., Modrak and Pandian (2010). Subsequently, the best

Then, the objective function for the given flow shop scheduling problem can be formally expressed as minimisation of the so-called Remaining Slack (RS) value, i.e.:

$$RS \rightarrow \min, \text{ while } RS \in \langle 0, \infty \rangle, \tag{2}$$

where

$$RS = DD - C_{max} \tag{3}$$

This objective function will be used to identify optimal transport batch sizes. The procedure will be further described in detail through the theoretical case study, where, after optimisation of transport batch size for groups of daily orders, the optimal production-planning schedule will be defined and its graphical model shown.

The proposed methodology for the production planning uses specialised software (see link in the reference list), which generates graphical and numerical outputs according to defined input data. In the next section, the description of developed software will be explained due to its more straightforward and faster application.

Characteristics of the Developed Software

The software applied in this research is available online as a helpful tool for generating outputs in the form of tables and graphs based on the input data (Online computing software, see link in the reference list). Input data includes:

- matrix $m \times n$ containing processing times in seconds for each job (Figure 1a),
- number of processing operations for each job within one transport batch size (Figure 1b),
- number of transport batches for each job, (Figure 1c),
- selected jobs sequence numbered by order (Figure 1d).

Figure 1. The table format for insertion of input data.

Its application in the first step needs to copy input data in the form of Microsoft Office Excel Table and paste them in the input data window. A flowchart of how to generate outputs is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Software flowcharts with acquired input data.

Subsequently, it is possible to generate results in the form of the following outputs:

- Information table with summarised input data to check the completeness of input data,
- Automatically generated optimal sequence of the jobs in order to minimise the makespan.
- Maximum and minimum makespan values,
- In-Out Table for the optimal sequence of the jobs,
- The Gantt chart of the generated schedule for the makespan minimisation
- Graphs for each job showing the relation between the number of process parts (products) and processing time in seconds.

In the subsequent section, its functionalities are presented through the hypothetical case study.

RESULTS

Theoretical Case Study

Here, the theoretical case study demonstrates the application of the proposed scheduling method by using specialised software.

Let us have the manufacturing system containing eight machines or workstations (M), where three jobs marked as J1, J2, and J3 are produced. We will consider the job sequence J3 - J2 - J1 according to the Cmax criterion. Table 1, in which m x n problem is adapted from (Zhang et al., 2009), shows the processing times of each job (n) on each workstation (m) in seconds.

Table 1. Processing times for the case study in seconds.

m x n	J ₁	J ₂	J ₃
M1	860	670	860
M2	649	1 018	756
M3	811	870	653
M4	770	831	750
M5	979	510	879
M6	487	986	457
M7	534	1148	534
M8	610	820	876

*m=workstation, n= job, (J1, J2, J3) = job sequencing

Gathered orders are, as the first step, summarised and categorised into groups of daily orders with quantities as follows. For Day #1, Day #4, and Day #5 are job quantities Qp1 = 125, Qp2 = 73, and Qp3 = 47, for Day #2 are job quantities Qp1 = 83, Qp2 = 45, and Qp3 = 29, and for Day #3 are job quantities Qp1 = 169, Qp2 = 87, and Qp3 = 45.

As can be seen from these quantities, the number of ordered daily quantities needs to be modified because the quantities are not in the form of rounding to the nearest 10, as described in the third section of this paper. Firstly, in the case of Day #1, the ordered quantities will be divided as follows, Qp1 into Qp1A = 120, and Qp1B = 5, where QT1B = 5, and L1B = 1; Qp2 is divided into Qp2A = 70, and Qp2B = 3, where QT2B = 3, and L2B = 1; quantity of Qp3 is separated into Qp3A = 40 and Qp3B = 7, where QT3B = 7, and L3B = 1. Analogically, this procedure is applied for the rest of the daily orders, and the modified quantities are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Modified quantities of daily orders.

Job quantity	Days				
	Day #1	Day #2	Day #3	Day #4	Day #5
Qp1A	120	80	160	120	120
Qp1B	5	3	9	5	5
Qp2A	70	40	80	70	70
Qp2B	3	5	7	3	3
Qp3A	40	20	40	40	40
Qp3B	7	9	5	7	7

Determination of due dates

For the determination of DD for the given five daily orders, as the first step, the data from Tables 1 and 2 will be used to calculate the minimum and maximum Cmax for individual daily orders. Maximum Cmax values are useful only for comparison of their upper bounds against lower bounds. For this purpose, developed software will be used. Input data for a software application in case of calculation of Cmax and generation of the Gantt chart for the same groups of orders of Day #1, Day #4 and Day #5 have to be structured as shown in Figure 3.

Input Data						
All in One BOX (Copy and Paste Input Data (selected table) from Excel here)						
860	860	670	670	860	860	
649	649	1018	1018	756	756	
811	811	870	870	653	653	
770	770	831	831	750	750	
979	979	510	510	879	879	
487	487	986	986	457	457	
534	534	1148	1148	534	534	
610	610	820	820	876	876	
1	1	1	1	1	1	
120	5	70	3	40	7	
6	5	4	3	2	1	

Figure 3. An example of the arrangement of input data for the software (created by Print Screen).

The software outputs for the groups of orders of Day #2, and Day #3 are obtained in the same way. Further, it is assumed that production takes place in three shifts, for 24 hours. Output values of minimum and maximum Cmax for each day are summarised. Minimum Cmax = 2.47 days and maximum Cmax = 9 days for the order of Day #1, Day #4 and Day #5. Minimum Cmax = 1.63 days and maximum Cmax = 5.95 days for the order of Day #2. Minimum Cmax = 3.06 days and maximum Cmax = 11.77 days for the order of Day #3.

In order to estimate DD, the average value of minimal makespans is rounded to a higher integer and then, $DD \geq 3$.

Determination of transport batch size for individual jobs

In this step, optimal QT for specific jobs will be identified. The procedure for the selection of optimal QT is explained in a few steps for days with the same number of orders, i.e., Day #1, Day #4, and Day #5, as was described in the third section.

In the following step, all possible number of transport batches for Qp1A, Qp2A, and Qp3A, can be identified as values 1, 2, 5 and 10.

Subsequently, minimum Cmax values for all alternatives are calculated through the software.

Table 3. All possible Li and QT_i for Day #1, Day #4 and Day #5.

Number of transport batches alt.	Qp1	Qp1A		Qp1B		Qp2	Qp2A		PB2B		Qp3	Qp3A		Qp3B		Cmax (days)
		QT1A	L1A	QT1B	L1B		QT2A	L2A	QT2B	L2B		QT3A	L3A	QT3B	L3B	
Alt. 1	125	120	1	5	1	73	70	1	3	1	47	40	1	7	1	9
Alt. 2		60	2	5	1		35	2	3	1		20	2	7	1	5,66
Alt. 3		24	5	5	1		14	5	3	1		8	5	7	1	3,66
Alt. 4		12	10	5	1		7	10	3	1		4	10	7	1	2,99

Finally, the results of RS values using equation (3) are enumerated for all alternatives. RS = - 6 days for Alternative 1, RS = -2.66 days for Alternative 2, RS = - 0.66 days for Alternative 3, and RS = 0.01 days for Alternative 4. According to these results, the optimal unified QT4 is identified as Alternative 4. Its value equals 2.99 days (Table 3), which satisfied predetermined DD according to objective function determined in expression (2).

The optimal QT_i can be generated for the remaining daily orders in the same way. Summarised results with optimal QT_i, where optimal L_i for Day #2 equals to 10, and for Day #3 equals to 40, are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Optimal QT_i for five daily orders.

Orders by days	Optimal transport batch size						Final Cmax (days)
	QT _{1A}	QT _{1B}	QT _{2A}	QT _{2B}	QT _{3A}	QT _{3B}	
Day #1	12	5	7	3	4	7	2.99
Day #2	8	3	4	5	2	9	1.97
Day #3	4	9	2	7	1	5	3.30
Day #4	12	5	7	3	4	7	2.99
Day #5	12	5	7	3	4	7	2.99

As can be seen from Table 8, the final makespan for groups of orders of Day #3 is over DD. Then, we have two possibilities, to leave the scheduled as it is, with given tardiness, or to split the daily order into two sub-orders, which would be processed in parallel. The next subsection will describe the first possibility.

Production planning and capacity modelling

Finally, it is possible to generate Gantt charts using the software that present common graphical interpretation for production scheduling and capacity modelling. The multi Gantt chart for the orders of Days #1 - #5 is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The multi Gantt chart for selected daily orders.

In a given case, three lines are assumed, and the schedule is continuously set up into the whole days. Production requirements from Day #1 can be started to produce on the production Line #1, by starting on the second day and finishing on the fourth day. Order from Day #2 can be started to produce on the production Line #2, while it will also be finished on the fourth day. It is possible to continue in the same way for orders from Day #3, Day #4, and Day #5, while orders from Day #4 and Day #5 can be produced on Lines #1 and 2 because the previous production was completed the day before. This is a schedule for five daily orders which can be finished to eight days using the defined three production lines.

Idle time of Line #2 on the fifth day can be utilised for the second sub-order of Day #3. Then, the tardiness would be eliminated. The splitting of the any daily order can be supported by the software. To be specific, the order of Day#3 could be split up into two sub-orders by the following manner, as shown in Supplement A. Firstly, we will use outputs of the software in the form of Gantt chart representing the sub-schedule for orders of Day#3 (Supplement A (c)). One can see from the Gantt chart where DD is depicted that several transport batches of different jobs will be completed after DD. In order to identify all such transport batches, the available table with in-out times of each transport batch of given job on each machine can be used (Supplement A (b)). Then, we can exactly determine the number of transport batches of each job with tardiness. Namely, they are five transport batches of J1, four transport batches of J2 and four transport batches of J3, totally 32 uncompleted parts.

DISCUSSIONS

Obtained and above referred results provide evidence that proposed idea to split QP of all jobs to the same or almost the same transport batches is not only useful, but also practicable in real time operation.

Further, as it has been shown in previous section, sometimes can occur specific situations that require reorganizing customer orders from one day to another with the aim to keep due dates in mind. Then, reorganization of multi Gantt charts can be easily reached by supporting software, by which single Gantt charts are generated and in-out times of each transport batch of given job on each machine are enumerated as shown in Supplement A.

By satisfying the due date constraint, the proposed solution guarantees to cover the large variety of demands. On the other hand, by satisfying the time horizon constraint, the solution assures that the products are on-time delivered to the customer, and this will increase the competitiveness of the mass customization producer. Moreover, the lower production costs obtained thanks to the lower number of changeovers can increase competitiveness and profit.

The important rule of proposed scheduling method is determination of optimal smallest scheduling periods, e.g., days. Idle time between the end and the beginning of the production can be used, e.g., for quality control operations.

The proposed method enables to model the production schedules continually and eliminate of stochastic effects in the production. Developed software is free and available online through the link in reference list. Obviously, this software cannot cover all possible scheduling tasks in terms of mass customization (Chandra and Kamrani, 2004). Its main limitation lays in the fact that setup times are included in the processing times, or are even ignored. Moreover, each machine can process, at most, one job at a time. Future research directions may be also oriented on incorporation different constraints such as the minimal number of changeovers, the elimination of idle times, the flow time minimization, etc.

Moreover, our next effort will be also focused on verification of this method in different manufacturing conditions.

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Supplement A

- a) Table with in-out times of each QT of given job on each machine of the order of the Day #3.
- b) Gantt chart of the jobs sequence on the machines of the order of the Day #3.
- c) Input data of the order of the Day #3.

	M1		M2		M3		M4		M5		M6		M7		M8	
Job	In	Out														
1	0	360	420	600	660	900	1135	1135	1505	1940	1940	2175	2175	2320	2320	2470
2	360	540	600	900	1135	1135	1505	1505	1940	1940	2175	2175	2320	2320	2470	2470
3	540	900	900	1350	1350	1800	1800	2320	2320	2770	2770	3220	3220	3670	3670	3670
4	900	1135	1350	1650	1650	2100	2100	2550	2550	3000	3000	3450	3450	3900	3900	3900
5	1135	1350	1650	1965	1965	2415	2415	2865	2865	3315	3315	3765	3765	4215	4215	4215
6	1350	1575	1965	2280	2280	2730	2730	3180	3180	3630	3630	4080	4080	4530	4530	4530
7	1575	1800	2280	2595	2595	3045	3045	3495	3495	3945	3945	4395	4395	4845	4845	4845
8	1800	2025	2595	2910	2910	3360	3360	3810	3810	4260	4260	4710	4710	5160	5160	5160
9	2025	2250	2910	3225	3225	3675	3675	4125	4125	4575	4575	5025	5025	5475	5475	5475
10	2250	2475	3225	3540	3540	3990	3990	4440	4440	4890	4890	5340	5340	5790	5790	5790
11	2475	2700	3540	3855	3855	4305	4305	4755	4755	5205	5205	5655	5655	6105	6105	6105
12	2700	2925	3855	4170	4170	4620	4620	5070	5070	5520	5520	5970	5970	6420	6420	6420
13	2925	3150	4170	4485	4485	4935	4935	5385	5385	5835	5835	6285	6285	6735	6735	6735
14	3150	3375	4485	4800	4800	5250	5250	5700	5700	6150	6150	6600	6600	7050	7050	7050
15	3375	3600	4800	5115	5115	5610	5610	6060	6060	6510	6510	6960	6960	7410	7410	7410
16	3600	3825	5115	5430	5430	5880	5880	6330	6330	6780	6780	7230	7230	7680	7680	7680
17	3825	4050	5430	5745	5745	6210	6210	6660	6660	7110	7110	7560	7560	8010	8010	8010
18	4050	4275	5745	6060	6060	6540	6540	6990	6990	7440	7440	7890	7890	8340	8340	8340
19	4275	4500	6060	6375	6375	6810	6810	7260	7260	7710	7710	8160	8160	8610	8610	8610
20	4500	4725	6375	6690	6690	7140	7140	7590	7590	8040	8040	8490	8490	8940	8940	8940
21	4725	4950	6690	7005	7005	7470	7470	7920	7920	8370	8370	8820	8820	9270	9270	9270
22	4950	5175	7005	7320	7320	7770	7770	8220	8220	8670	8670	9120	9120	9570	9570	9570
23	5175	5400	7320	7635	7635	8085	8085	8535	8535	8985	8985	9435	9435	9885	9885	9885
24	5400	5625	7635	7950	7950	8415	8415	8865	8865	9315	9315	9765	9765	10215	10215	10215
25	5625	5850	7950	8265	8265	8685	8685	9135	9135	9585	9585	10035	10035	10485	10485	10485
26	5850	6075	8265	8580	8580	8995	8995	9445	9445	9895	9895	10345	10345	10795	10795	10795
27	6075	6300	8580	8895	8895	9305	9305	9755	9755	10205	10205	10655	10655	11105	11105	11105
28	6300	6525	8895	9210	9210	9615	9615	10065	10065	10515	10515	10965	10965	11415	11415	11415
29	6525	6750	9210	9525	9525	9925	9925	10375	10375	10825	10825	11275	11275	11725	11725	11725
30	6750	6975	9525	9840	9840	10235	10235	10685	10685	11135	11135	11585	11585	12035	12035	12035
31	6975	7200	9840	10155	10155	10545	10545	10995	10995	11445	11445	11895	11895	12345	12345	12345
32	7200	7425	10155	10470	10470	10855	10855	11305	11305	11755	11755	12205	12205	12655	12655	12655
33	7425	7650	10470	10785	10785	11165	11165	11615	11615	12065	12065	12515	12515	12965	12965	12965
34	7650	7875	10785	11100	11100	11525	11525	11975	11975	12425	12425	12875	12875	13325	13325	13325
35	7875	8100	11100	11415	11415	11835	11835	12285	12285	12735	12735	13185	13185	13635	13635	13635
36	8100	8325	11415	11730	11730	12145	12145	12595	12595	13045	13045	13495	13495	13945	13945	13945
37	8325	8550	11730	12045	12045	12455	12455	12905	12905	13355	13355	13805	13805	14255	14255	14255
38	8550	8775	12045	12360	12360	12765	12765	13215	13215	13665	13665	14115	14115	14565	14565	14565
39	8775	9000	12360	12675	12675	13075	13075	13525	13525	13975	13975	14425	14425	14875	14875	14875
40	9000	9225	12675	12990	12990	13385	13385	13835	13835	14285	14285	14735	14735	15185	15185	15185
41	9225	9450	12990	13305	13305	13695	13695	14145	14145	14595	14595	15045	15045	15495	15495	15495
42	9450	9675	13305	13620	13620	14055	14055	14505	14505	14955	14955	15405	15405	15855	15855	15855
43	9675	9900	13620	13935	13935	14365	14365	14815	14815	15265	15265	15715	15715	16165	16165	16165
44	9900	10125	13935	14250	14250	14675	14675	15125	15125	15575	15575	16025	16025	16475	16475	16475
45	10125	10350	14250	14565	14565	14935	14935	15385	15385	15835	15835	16285	16285	16735	16735	16735
46	10350	10575	14565	14880	14880	15245	15245	15695	15695	16145	16145	16595	16595	17045	17045	17045
47	10575	10800	14880	15195	15195	15555	15555	16005	16005	16455	16455	16905	16905	17355	17355	17355
48	10800	11025	15195	15510	15510	15815	15815	16265	16265	16715	16715	17165	17165	17615	17615	17615
49	11025	11250	15510	15825	15825	16125	16125	16575	16575	17025	17025	17475	17475	17925	17925	17925
50	11250	11475	15825	16140	16140	16435	16435	16885	16885	17335	17335	17785	17785	18235	18235	18235
51	11475	11700	16140	16455	16455	16745	16745	17195	17195	17645	17645	18095	18095	18545	18545	18545
52	11700	11925	16455	16770	16770	17055	17055	17505	17505	17955	17955	18405	18405	18855	18855	18855
53	11925	12150	16770	17085	17085	17365	17365	17815	17815	18265	18265	18715	18715	19165	19165	19165
54	12150	12375	17085	17400	17400	17685	17685	18135	18135	18585	18585	19035	19035	19485	19485	19485
55	12375	12600	17400	17715	17715	18005	18005	18455	18455	18905	18905	19355	19355	19805	19805	19805
56	12600	12825	17715	18030	18030	18315	18315	18765	18765	19215	19215	19665	19665	20115	20115	20115
57	12825	13050	18030	18345	18345	18625	18625	19075	19075	19525	19525	19975	19975	20425	20425	20425
58	13050	13275	18345	18660	18660	18905	18905	19355	19355	19805	19805	20255	20255	20705	20705	20705
59	13275	13500	18660	18975	18975	19215	19215	19665	19665	20115	20115	20565	20565	21015	21015	21015
60	13500	13725	18975	19290	19290	19535	19535	19985	19985	20435	20435	20885	20885	21335	21335	21335
61	13725	13950	19290	19605	19605	19845	19845	20295	20295	20745	20745	21195	21195	21645	21645	21645
62	13950	14175	19605	19920	19920	20165	20165	20615	20615	21065	21065	21515	21515	21965	21965	21965
63	14175	14400	19920	20235	20235	20405	20405	20855	20855	21305	21305	21755	21755	22205	22205	22205
64	14400	14625	20235	20550	20550	20715	20715	21165	21165	21615	21615	22065	22065	22515	22515	22515
65	14625	14850	20550	20865	20865	21025	21025	21475	21475	21925	21925	22375	22375	22825	22825	22825
66	14850	15075	20865	21180	21180	21335	21335	21785	21785	22235	22235	22685	22685	23135	23135	23135
67	15075	15300	21180	21495	21495	21645	21645	22095	22095	22545	22545	22995	22995	23445	23445	23445
68	15300	15525	21495	21810	21810	21955	21955	22405	22405	22855	22855	23305	23305	23755	23755	23755
69	15525	15750	21810	22125	22125	22265	22265	22755	22755	23205	23205	23655	23655	24105	24105	24105
70	15750	15975	22125	22440	22440	22575	22575	23065	23065	23515	23515	23965	23965	24415	24415	24415
71	15975	16200	22440	22755	22755	22885	22885	23375	23375	23825	23825	24275	24275	24725	24725	24725
72	16200	16425	22755	23070	23070	23195	23195	23685	23685							